

DairyPersonNet: A dataset of people in dairy processing environments for industrial computer vision research

Mirko Gueregat Henriquez
Universidad Austral de Chile
<https://orcid.org/0009-0002-6537-8170>

Abstract

This article presents DairyPersonNet, a dataset designed for person detection in dairy processing environments. The dataset was collected using CCTV cameras installed in a dairy production plant located in Valdivia, Chile. Frames were extracted from RTSP video streams acquired from three cameras installed in two different functional areas of the plant: two cameras in the processing room and one camera in the hygiene room.

DairyPersonNet contains 3396 labeled images and 11707 bounding box annotations corresponding to the class `person`. The dataset was acquired across five capture days and organized into train, validation and test subsets.

The dataset was designed to support industrial computer vision research tasks such as worker detection, occupancy estimation, activity monitoring, and compliance verification in food processing facilities. All images were manually annotated using the CVAT annotation platform and exported in YOLO format. To preserve worker privacy, a visual anonymization step based on eye-region blurring was applied before public release.

The dataset is publicly available through IEEE DataPort and is intended to support reproducible benchmarking for person detection models in industrial food production environments.

Specifications Table

Subject area	Computer Vision / Industrial Monitoring
Specific subject area	Person detection in dairy processing plants
Type of data	RGB images and bounding box annotations
How data were acquired	Frames extracted from RTSP CCTV streams
Data format	JPG images and YOLO annotation files
Number of images	3396
Number of annotated instances	11707
Classes	person
Cameras	3 CCTV cameras
Capture days	5 days
Data source location	Valdivia, Chile
Data accessibility	IEEE DataPort (https://dx.doi.org/10.21227/17vg-es44)

Value of the Data

- The dataset provides real-world industrial imagery captured in a dairy production facility.
- It includes challenging visual conditions such as occlusions, reflective surfaces, mixed lighting and viewpoint variability.

- The dataset can be used for training and benchmarking person detection models in industrial food production settings.
- It supports research on worker monitoring, occupancy estimation and industrial computer vision systems for food safety environments.
- The dataset includes images captured from three CCTV cameras distributed across different plant areas, enabling multi-view analysis.

1 Background

Food safety in dairy production requires strict monitoring of worker activity and hygiene practices. Human presence inside critical production and hygiene areas may introduce contamination risks if protocols are not followed properly [1].

Computer vision systems have increasingly been explored for automated monitoring in food safety and hygiene contexts [2, 3]. In addition, industrial monitoring based on deep learning has shown potential for compliance and safety verification in workplace environments [4].

However, generic person detection datasets do not usually reflect the visual characteristics of dairy processing environments, such as reflective metallic equipment, constrained indoor spaces, worker clothing, and CCTV viewpoints. DairyPersonNet was developed to address this gap by providing a domain-specific dataset for person detection in dairy production facilities.

2 Data Description

DairyPersonNet contains 3396 labeled images and 11707 person annotations. Each visible worker in the image is annotated with a bounding box corresponding to the class **person**.

The images were extracted from RTSP streams recorded by CCTV cameras installed inside a dairy processing plant in Valdivia, Chile. According to the acquisition setup, two cameras observed the processing room and one camera observed the hygiene room.

The dataset includes images captured over five dates identified from the image filenames:

- 20250528
- 20250529
- 20250530
- 20250623
- 20250624

Annotations were created using the Computer Vision Annotation Tool (CVAT) [5] and exported in YOLO object detection format [6].

2.1 Dataset summary

Attribute	Value
Total images	3396
Total annotations	11707
Number of classes	1
Training images	2716
Validation images	339
Test images	341
Train annotations	9327
Validation annotations	1249
Test annotations	1131
Annotation format	YOLO
Image format	JPG
Camera sources	3 CCTV cameras
Capture days	5
Location	Dairy processing plant, Valdivia, Chile

2.2 Annotation format

Annotations follow the YOLO format:

```
class_id x_center y_center width height
```

where all values are normalized relative to image dimensions.

2.3 Dataset structure

```
DairyPersonNet/  
  images/  
    train/  
    val/  
    test/  
  labels/  
    train/  
    val/  
    test/  
  dataset.yaml
```

2.4 Example dataset images

Example images from the dataset are shown in Fig. 1. The images illustrate typical visual conditions observed in the dairy processing environment, including occlusions, reflective surfaces, and variations in worker distance from the cameras.

Figure 1: Example images from the DairyPersonNet dataset showing annotated workers in dairy production environments.

2.5 Bounding box spatial distribution

The spatial distribution of bounding box centers across the image space is illustrated in Fig. 2. The plot highlights the most frequent worker locations observed across the three CCTV view-points.

Figure 2: Spatial distribution of bounding box centers across the image space for the **person** class. The plot summarizes the typical worker locations observed in the three CCTV viewpoints.

2.6 Object size distribution

The distribution of normalized bounding box areas is shown in Fig. 3. This histogram reflects variability in worker distance from the cameras and viewpoint-dependent scale changes present in the dataset.

Figure 3: Histogram of normalized bounding box areas for person annotations in DairyPersonNet.

2.7 Image distribution by capture day

The number of images captured on each acquisition day is summarized in Table 1. These values were inferred from the timestamps encoded in the image filenames.

Capture day	Images
20250528	768
20250529	701
20250530	1742
20250623	35
20250624	150

Table 1: Distribution of images across capture days inferred from timestamps in filenames.

The same information is visualized in Fig. 4. The histogram reflects the sampling process used during frame extraction from the CCTV video streams.

Figure 4: Distribution of images by capture day, inferred from the timestamps encoded in the filenames.

2.8 Temporal information encoded in filenames

Image filenames encode the timestamp of the original frame extracted from the video streams using the format:

`YYYYMMDDHHMMSS_UUID.jpg`

For example, a filename beginning with:

`20250530105917`

represents an image captured on May 30, 2025 at 10:59:17.

This naming convention preserves temporal traceability of frames extracted from the CCTV streams.

3 Experimental Design, Materials and Methods

3.1 Dataset acquisition workflow

Figure 5: Workflow used to generate the DairyPersonNet dataset.

3.2 Data acquisition

Video streams were obtained from three CCTV cameras installed in a dairy production plant. Two cameras were located in the processing room and one camera was located in the hygiene room. Frames were extracted from RTSP streams to generate still images representing routine operational conditions.

Based on cache metadata associated with the labeled data, the dataset contains three recurrent native image resolutions, which is consistent with the three-camera acquisition setup.

3.3 Annotation process

All visible workers were manually annotated with bounding boxes using the CVAT annotation platform [5]. The annotations were exported in YOLO format [6].

To preserve privacy, images intended for public release were anonymized by applying eye-region blurring.

3.4 Dataset split

The published dataset is organized into train, validation and test subsets:

- Train: 2716 images
- Validation: 339 images

- Test: 341 images

The split includes images acquired on multiple dates in each subset. Therefore, the published partition should be described as an official train/validation/test split rather than a strictly day-exclusive partition.

3.5 Example dataset usage

A preliminary baseline experiment was conducted using a YOLO-based detector to demonstrate potential dataset usage for person detection in industrial environments [6].

Training configuration:

- Model: YOLOv11n
- Input resolution: 640
- Training epochs: 100

This example is intended to illustrate how the dataset can be used for benchmarking and transfer learning in industrial computer vision applications.

4 Limitations

- The dataset was collected in a single dairy production facility.
- Only one semantic class (**person**) is annotated.
- The dataset covers a limited number of plant areas and camera viewpoints.
- Although the dataset spans multiple dates, the official split is not strictly exclusive by capture day.

Future work may extend the dataset by including additional facilities, more capture days, more camera viewpoints and complementary annotation tasks such as activity or PPE labeling.

Ethics Statement

The dataset was collected with authorization from the collaborating dairy company. Images were anonymized using eye-region blurring to protect worker identity. No personal identifiers are included in the released data.

CRedit Author Statement

Mirko H. Gueregat: Conceptualization, Data curation, Methodology, Software, Investigation, Visualization, Writing – original draft.

Luis Veas Castillo: Supervision, Methodology, Writing – review & editing.

Christian Lazo Ramirez: Supervision, Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing.

Data Availability

The DairyPersonNet dataset is publicly available at IEEE DataPort [7]:

<https://dx.doi.org/10.21227/17vg-es44>

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this article.

References

- [1] Maria Kousta, Marios Mataragas, Panagiotis Skandamis, and Eleftherios H. Drosinos. Prevalence and sources of cheese contamination with pathogens at farm and processing levels. *Food Control*, 21(6):805–815, 2010.
- [2] I.-C. Chen, C.-H. Chi, and H.-H. Ku. Deep learning for the detection of good hygienic practices control measures for food handlers. *Food Control*, 171:111041, 2025.
- [3] Zhe Liu, Shuzhe Wang, Yudong Zhang, Yichen Feng, Jiajia Liu, and Hengde Zhu. Artificial intelligence in food safety: A decade review and bibliometric analysis. *Foods*, 12(6), 2023.
- [4] Arso M. Vukicevic, Marko Djapan, Velibor Isailovic, Danko Milasinovic, Marija Savkovic, and Pavle Milosevic. Generic compliance of industrial ppe by using deep learning techniques. *Safety Science*, 148:105646, 2022.
- [5] CVAT.ai Corporation. Computer vision annotation tool (cvat), 2024.
- [6] Joseph Redmon and Ali Farhadi. Yolov3: An incremental improvement. *arXiv*, arXiv:1804.02767, 2018.
- [7] Mirko H. Gueregat. Dairypersonnet: A dataset of people in dairy processing environments for industrial computer vision research, 2026.